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TOXICOGENIC PROPERTIES OF MICROMYCETES IN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS

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Summary: *Most toxigenic fungi can survive in the soil for several months, and many of them feed saprotrophically in the presence of nutrients and certain environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, etc.). Mycotoxins and their producers affect all the most important indicators of soil quality (productivity, properties and health). Microscopic fungi that infect agricultural products during the growing season of plants, as well as during storage, can enter food products and animal feed, contaminating them with their toxic metabolites - mycotoxins.*

Keywords: *Toxigenic fungi, mycotoxin, toxigenic properties, metabolites, environmental conditions*

Introduction: Microscopic fungi are the most important component of soil mycobiota. Micromycetes, which constitute more than 50% of the total biomass of soil microorganisms, play a key role in the processes occurring in the soil [1;5]. They decompose organic matter of various origins and compositions and produce many biologically active compounds, including enzymes, vitamins, organic acids, antibiotics and, most importantly, toxins.

The wide distribution of fungi in various types of soils, in the rhizosphere of plants, in agricultural soils, in the air and in the human habitat is due to their adaptation to various conditions, including anthropogenic substrates. This is also facilitated by their rapid growth, intensive reproduction, method of propagation and highly efficient labile metabolism. Compounds with different chemical compositions and properties can serve as substrates for fungi. Fungi play an important role in the microbiological weathering of carbonate rocks and the formation of carbon dioxide fluxes into the atmosphere, and in the self-recovery of soils after anthropogenic impact.

Fungi belonging to various systematic groups, including indeterminate fungi, ascomycetes, zygomycetes, oomycetes and entomopathogenic fungi, have the ability to synthesize toxins. The accumulation of fungal toxins in the soil causes toxicosis, which results in a decrease in plant productivity. In agriculture, this phenomenon is known as soil "fatigue" [4;7]. Anthropogenic influences such as salinization, soil pollution with oil or long-term use of mineral fertilizers can lead to a change in the composition of fungal communities in favor of toxin-producing species and the accumulation of mycotoxins. During the nitrification process, fungi produce toxic compounds from the group of hydroxamic acids, which can cause soil toxicosis. The synthesis of these compounds is enhanced by nitrification inhibitors.

Toxigenic fungi infect agricultural plants during the growing season, resulting in the contamination of the product with mycotoxins, which can cause serious diseases (mycoses and mycotoxicoses) in humans and animals during the consumption of plant products and feed. The problems posed by toxigenic micromycetes, both theoretically and practically, are of a general biological nature and should be taken into account when developing environmental protection and food safety strategies.

Modern technologies of oil production, transportation and processing do not exclude the possibility of oil and its processed products entering the environment. Hydrocarbons pollute the soil, significantly negatively affecting all its properties. Soil pollution with oil creates a new ecological situation. The general characteristics of oil-contaminated soils result in a change in the number and species composition of microscopic fungi living in these soils [2;3].

Little is known about the accumulation and subsequent transformation of mycotoxins in the soil, although their distribution in food products has been actively studied in the past and is currently

being studied. Mycotoxins, accumulating in plants infected with fungi, can enter the soil through the roots, as well as after harvesting, through stems and grains remaining in the field. It is known that the content of mycotoxins in the soil reaches micrograms: zearalenone - up to 72.1, deoxynivalenol - up to 32.1, ochratoxin A - up to 23.7, nivalenol - up to 6.7, aflatoxin - up to 5.5 µg/kg of soil .

The concentration of mycotoxins in the soil varies from year to year depending on weather conditions. The most important factors contributing to the accumulation of mycotoxins are temperature and humidity, which increase the activity of oxidative and hydrolytic enzymes and create favorable conditions for the reproduction of micromycetes.

In high-temperature, humid tropical and subtropical regions, *Aspergillus* spp., which are producers of aflatoxin and ochratoxin, are widespread. *Penicillium* spp., among which there are many dangerous plant pathogens, grow and produce toxins in a wide range of temperatures, are able to adapt to different conditions and spread widely. The differences in the optimal temperatures for the synthesis of ochratoxin in the micromycetes *P.verrucosum* (4-31°C) and *A.ochraceus* (12-37°C) explain why the former predominate in temperate regions of the globe, and the latter in subtropical and tropical areas.

Phylogenetic studies have shown that toxigenic properties have been formed in molds as a result of long-term evolution. The results of the genome sequencing of 93 species of *Fusarium* revealed the presence of genes responsible for the synthesis of 26 groups of secondary metabolites.

Modern urbanization is accompanied by significant changes in soil microbiota. Especially dangerous are toxic microscopic fungi that can produce mycotoxins - substances that have a pronounced carcinogenic, mutagenic and immunosuppressive effect. In urban conditions, especially in areas with poor ecological conditions, favorable conditions have been created for the development of such organisms. The aim of this study is to study the species composition and mycotoxic activity of toxigenic fungi in urban soils [6].

Materials and methods: The areas from which samples were taken for the study differ from each other both in terms of the total area of the territory, the nature of economic activity, and the nature of technogenic impacts on the soil and vegetation of the territory. During the study, samples were taken from soil and plant sources.

Methods for studying toxigenic fungi are extremely diverse, and for this purpose, either the substrate on which the fungus lives, or itself, or toxic metabolites synthesized by the fungi are used. Currently, the toxigenicity of fungi is determined using each of the mentioned sources. Determining toxigenicity by metabolites synthesized by fungi is an extremely complex and energy-consuming process, and is not considered suitable for screening. Therefore, it was considered appropriate to use a method based on the direct use of fungi themselves in the course of the studies. For this purpose, the species composition of toxigenic fungi was determined in relation to plants (phytotoxic activity).

Raw soil from the Central Botanical Garden located in Baku was used as a control option. In addition, soil samples contaminated with oil to varying degrees were taken from the vicinity of oil wells located in the Binagadi and Sabail districts of the city. Samples were also taken from Chambarekand Park, a recreational area. Samples taken during different seasons were cultivated in agarized malt juice (5-6 days), which is a standard nutrient medium. The number of micromycetes that passed the incubation period was calculated. To determine the structure of the soil micromycetes complex, the frequency of occurrence in space and time, as well as the number of species, were used.

Results and discussion. It was determined that the studied soils are characterized by a relatively high number and species composition of fungi participating in the formation of mycobiota in the vegetation. At the same time, toxigenic species predominated in the formation of mycobiota in the autumn season, with toxic fungi accounting for 53% of the mycobiota recorded in the soil and 62.1% of those recorded in plants. As a result of the study of the phytotoxic activity of the 32 identified species, *T.herbarum* (3%) and *P.circinan* (5%) fungi showed weak, *F.oxysporum* (46%), *F. verticillioides* (45%) and *P. chrysogenum* (39%) showed high toxic activity.

During the study of the mycocomplex of soils exposed to natural and various technogenic influences, it became clear that technogenic influences lead to both a decrease in the species diversity

of the mycocomplex inherent to soils and a change in eco-trophic relationships. Thus, changes resulting from technogenic impacts are characterized by the proliferation of specific strains of either opportunists or allergens in the fungal biota specific to each cenosis, and in all cases, the background level of toxigens characteristic of soils relatively clean from technogenic impacts increases.

Weather conditions have a great impact on both plants and micromycetes. Sharp fluctuations and unstable weather events, as well as the predicted global warming of the climate can significantly affect the structure of phytopathogenic complexes. With a change in the ratio of phytopathogenic species, the set of toxic metabolites in plants can change.

Determining the dynamics of phytopathogenic complexes, studying the factors affecting the transition of rare species of toxin-producing fungi to the category of dominants, will allow us to foresee the danger of accumulation of potential mycotoxins in the environment.

During the study, it was confirmed that mycotoxins are synthesized mainly by species belonging to the genera *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium*. Also, the species *Alternaria* spp., which is characterized by several sets of toxic metabolites, attracted our attention. The toxicological aspects of such metabolites are being actively studied.

Of particular note is the discovery of new mycotoxin producers among known toxigenic fungal species with a limited distribution range, which complicates the assessment of the potential risk of contamination of food raw materials with these mycotoxins [6].

Conclusion: Noting the diversity of molds of different families and genera and a wide range of toxic metabolites, it is necessary to consider their toxin production not only as a function of adaptation to environmental conditions, but also as a response of fungi to signals from the environment when changing their ecological niche. Plant products form the basis of the diet for all categories of the population, therefore, their negative effects on humans when contaminated with secondary metabolites of microscopic fungi are a priority issue in terms of food safety. The discovery of new and insufficiently studied strains of micromycetes and the enhancement of their toxic properties require studying the properties and ecology of emerging mycopathogens in order to substantiate effective ways to reduce their negative impact on the human and animal body, including the development and implementation of food safety criteria, new control technologies and measures to prevent food contamination.

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